

TURKEY CULTURE

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Annotation: This article include the spreading of English across the Globe such as social, political and cultural factors. Therefore it represents various of factors and how to spread and come across any kinds of factors.

Key words: English language, culture shock, culture, conflict, overseas, values, custom.

It is obviously known that culture shock is one of the most global issue which human come and cross it everywhere. It is an undeniable fact that «Culture shock» is a normal process of adapting to a new culture. It is a time when a person becomes aware of the differences and/or conflicts in values and customs between their home culture and the new culture they are in. Culture shock is some sort of adjustment you might feel when you are subject to a new way of living and an unfamiliar setting around you. Culture shock is feeling uncomfortable or sometimes even lonely when you are abroad in a new place (for example, during family holidays like Christmas). There are obvious examples of culture shock such as getting used to a different language, a different climate, a different transport system and different food customs. Less obvious examples of culture shock include acclimatising to: different hand gestures, different facial expressions and levels of eye contact.

Turkey has a collectivist culture whereby strong loyalty is shown to familial and social groups, as well as the broader nation. People's relationships with their neighbours and community are generally closer than what many from the English-speaking West experience.

One of the interesting facts about Turkey is that it lies both in Turkish and Asia. It has a very rich civilization that is influenced by many empires as well as different religions and ethnicities. Moreover, you will witness the marks of both European and Asian cultures in Turkey.

Kazakhstan is a hospitable and multi-ethnic country, but we do not know much about the culture of the peoples who live next to us.

Before the pandemic completely changes their traditional values, with the support of the European Union, we decided to talk about the traditions of our compatriots – Kazakhs, Uzbeks, Koreans, Uyghurs and Turks.

Like the Kazakhs, the Turks also have tea as a symbol of hospitality that allows people to get along. Every Turk drinks tea at least three times a day and believes that no conversation is complete without it.

Turkish tea is drunk in small special cups that look like tulips or pears. Mavrak bud, dried in special ways, is taken as the basis of tea – it not only makes tea delicious, but also activates its medicinal properties.

The Turkish people have been living in Kazakhstan for 75 years. According to 2018 data, their number is about 200 thousand people. Turks respect the peoples of Central Asia and consider this region the homeland of their ancestors.

During the heyday of the Soviet Union, Turks were oppressed by the government, and intellectuals were repressed. In 1956, they were given the opportunity to return to their historical homeland, but most of them decided to stay in Kazakhstan.

Due to the ethnic diversity of the country, they managed to preserve their cultural characteristics and traditions. Ethnocenters still play an important role in this. The main directions of the Turkish ethnocultural center are education, sports, culture, folklore and charity. During the quarantine, the representatives of the center not only adapted to the online format and organized Turkish language courses, but also managed to volunteer in various charitable organizations created both privately and in cooperation with the Assembly of the People of Kazakhstan. Turkish culture is also represented by an unofficial holiday called Hidirlez, which is celebrated on May 5-6. Its roots are in mythology, and the holiday itself is a mixture of old and new beliefs, combining Islam and Tengrianism. According to legends, on the night of May 5 to May 6, two prophets representing land and sea - Khidir and Ilyas meet. Thanks to their meeting, spring will come, and the prophets will bring with them joyful feelings and good news for all the inhabitants of the earth. Reminiscent of the Kazakh Nauruz holiday, the festival of prosperity and abundance is celebrated by Turkish communities: they take to the streets, gather in crowds, sing and dance. Young men and women light a fire, and women prepare dough products and take them to the street "for Khidir". During the celebration of Khidirlez, people usually choose a big tree, write their wishes on colorful handkerchiefs and tie them to the branches of the chosen tree. In wishes, you can ask for love, health, money - in general, anything you want for yourself and your loved ones. Kitchen The rich Turkish cuisine - koftika - combines various regional dishes - Mediterranean snacks and meat dishes. This is the entire history of cooking, combining the traditions of the peoples of Asia, the Caucasus and Europe. Turks enjoy light snacks called meze—salad, pickles, cheese, mushrooms, or the popular fried dumplings of seafood or meat known as borek. Turkish cuisine is rich in meat dishes. The usual type of kebab is jazz, thinly sliced kebab or small kofté. Another popular dish is dolma. Dolma is a dish of mixed meat and rice wrapped in grape or cabbage leaves. Turks also often eat seafood and vegetable dishes - for example, they can cook different dishes from a single eggplant. It is an indisputable fact that, wreful to come together with the family. Below you can see a list of national and religious holidays and public holidays celebrated in the country.

New Year: January 1st

National Sovereignty and Children's Day: April 23rd

Labor and Solidarity Day: May 1st

Atatürk Commemoration, Youth and Sports Day: May 19th

Democracy Day: July 15th

Victory Day: August 30th

Republic Day: October 29th

Ramadan Feast: Changes Yearly

Sacrifice Feast: Changes Yearly

By way of conclusion, culture is one of the integral part of country's life style. Though one may not be able to avoid experiencing culture shock, there are many ways to diminish its effects and accelerate its stages. Most importantly, keep an open mind. Don't enter a new culture with preconceived notions of what will be found. Making comparisons to the home country and new country should be avoided. Being open to new experiences and making an effort to learn the local language and culture can bring accelerated acceptance. Making connections and developing a support system provides individuals with help when necessary. Foreign experiences are not only opportunities to learn more about new cultures, but to share of and become better acquainted with oneself.

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